

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the *International Rice Research Newsletter* (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

IRAT170: a high-yielding, medium-duration upland rice for Nigeria

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We tested a number of breeding lines and varieties in 1983 upland rice zonal trials. IRAT170 was identified as a high-yielding variety with medium maturity and good plant type. It was evaluated with other selected entries in the advanced yield nurseries of the Coordinated Rice Evaluation Trials (CRET) in 1984 and 1985. In 1984 CRET, IRAT170 outyielded the commonly cultivated popular variety FARO 11 in four of the five locations.

In 1985, IRAT170 was superior to FARO 11 in all four locations (see table). Grain yield of IRAT170 was 37% higher than that of FARO 11.

IRAT170, a cross of IRAT13 and Palawan, was introduced from the Ivory Coast. It is medium tall (120 cm) with medium maturity (125 d). It has straight compact tillers and is resistant to lodging. Panicles are also compact with good spikelet fertility. Grains are long bold (B type) with nonglutinous endosperm. Cooking quality is better (amylose content 23.0%) than that of FARO 11 (amylose content 19.0%). It is also superior to FARO 11 in pest and disease resistance.

IRAT170 has been recommended for release for upland humid areas of Nigeria. □

Yield performance of IRAT170 in multilocal trials, Nigeria, 1984-85.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)						Increase over check (%)
	1984		1985		Mean		
	IRAT170	FARO 11	IRAT170	FARO 11	IRAT170	FARO 11	
Moor Plantation	3.6	3.4	5.6	3.7	4.6	3.6	28
IITA, Ibadan	1.4	0.6	0.6	0.1	1.0	0.4	150
Ikenne	2.6	2.1	2.6	1.9	2.6	2.0	30
Amakama	2.1	2.2	2.4	1.8	2.3	2.0	15
Oonne	2.7	1.7	—	—	2.7	1.7	59
Mean	2.4	2.0	2.8	1.9	2.6	1.9	37

Development of a rice composite for Nigeria

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Six rice varieties with similar agronomic characteristics but different reactions to diseases, lodging, and drought were selected and diallel-crossed in 1977. The varieties were commonly cultivated FARO 11, drought-tolerant E425 and OS4, FARO 25 with moderate resistance to brown spot, and high-yielding

IRAT1069m-1-2 and IR1154-243-1. The F₁ and F₂ populations were phenotypically similar to the parents except for variations in height and tolerance for drought and diseases. The F₂ crosses tested in 1978 were grouped into five classes (Table 1). These groups, with FARO 11 and a physical mixture of the six parent varieties as checks, were tested for 3 yr.

FAROX299, involving crosses of IRAT1069m-1-2 with other varieties, was shorter than FARO 11 and other crosses. It also showed higher

Table 1. Performance of composites in station trials, Moor Plantation, Ibadan, Nigeria, 1978.

Group	Designation	Cross	Average height (m)	Days to maturity	Panicles/m ²	Drought score	Blast score	Grain yield (t/ha)
a	FAROX298	Crosses of FARO 11	111	120	132	3	4	1.90
b	FAROX299	Crosses of IRAT1069m-1-2 with other varieties [excluding (a)]	105	119	144	2	2	2.12
c	FAROX300	Crosses of E425 and others excluding (a) and (b)	112	120	122	3	4	2.00
d	FAROX301	Crosses of OS4 and others excluding (a), (b), and (c)	109	120	132	3	4	1.90
e	FAROX302	Crosses of FARO 25 and others excluding (a), (b), (c), and (d)	108	123	132	3	4	2.00
f	FARO 11 (check)	—	111	120	132	4	3	2.00
g	Mixture (check)	Physical mixture of all parents in equal proportions	113	120	122	5	3	2.00
LSD	—	—	ns	ns	ns	—	—	ns
CV%	—	—	8.6	—	14.8	—	—	16.4

phenotypic acceptance and resistance to drought. During 1982 season, when total rainfall for the last 40 d of crop growth was 60 mm, FAROX299 produced the highest grain yield.

In 1984, the composite outyielded FARO 11 at three sites of a multilocation trial and produced as much yield as FARO 11 in one location (Table 2). At Onne, a high-rainfall area, FAROX299 showed resistance to sheath blight and leaf scald.

Table 2. Performance of FAROX299 in multilocation trials in Nigeria, 1984.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)					Mean
	1	2	3	4	5	
FAROX299	3.08	1.10	2.30	1.00	1.97	1.88
FARO 11 (check)	3.42	0.65	2.17	2.23	1.76	2.04
ITA117 (check)	2.35	0.25	1.58	1.48	1.74	1.48

^aLocation 1 = NCRI, Ibadan; 2 = IITA, Ibadan; 3 = Ikenne; 4 = Amakama, and 5 = Onne (IITA).

In 1986, the composite was recommended by the Nationally Coordinated Research Project for

release as a commercial variety for Nigeria. □

Paicos 1, a promising new rice for Manipur

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Paicos 1 is a promising semidwarf rice from a cross between local Phouren and RP8-9. It has wide adaptability to

irrigated, rainfed lowland, and transplanted conditions. It is photoperiod insensitive, matures in 135-140 d, and has high yield potential and stability. It outyielded popular rice varieties Punshi and Jaya (Table 1). The grains are long, slender, and translucent with local consumer

preference similar to that for Punshi.

Field trials during Jul-Aug and Nov-Dec 1981-84 showed high resistance to leaf and nodal blast and false smut (Table 2). □

Table 1. Performance of Paicos 1 in Imphal District, Manipur, India, 1981-85.

Variety	Av yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Panicles/m ²	Milling %	Length: width	Kernel elongation (mm)	Cooking quality
Paicos 1	6.2	138	290	68	3.44	1.98	Good
Punshi	5.9	135	291	65	3.10	1.83	Good
Jaya	5.8	138	290	70	2.86	1.76	Fair
CD at 5%	0.2						
CV%	9.0						

Table 2. Field reaction of Paicos 1 to blast and false smut, Manipur, India, 1981-85.

Variety	Reaction ^a			Rating ^a
	Leaf blast	Nodal blast	False smut	
Paicos 1	0-1	0-1	0-1	R
Punshi	2-3	2-3	2-3	S
Jaya	2-3	2-3	2-3	S

^aScored on the *Standard evaluation system rice* scale. R = resistant, S = susceptible.